

PLANNING

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

FUNDING

SEARCH

ACCESS

REFERENCE MANAGER

EXPERIMENTING

SHARING

ANALYZING

WRITING

CITING

PUBLICATION

= MAKING IT PUBLIC!

DISSEMINATION

OUTREACH

ASSESSMENT

EVALUATION

(PRE//POST)

OPEN WORKFLOW

posting brief
descriptions of ideas
in a very early phase

giving everybody
access to the needed
infrastructure (even
the wet lab)

recording steps and
inputs (reproducibility,
credit, products)

managing projects
openly

involving
public/patients etc. in
drafting research
proposals

crowdsourcing
research topic
prioritization

looking for research
partners in the Global
South

finding additional co-
authors by early
sharing of
manuscripts

sharing your
hypothesis before
starting the data
collection/analysis

making expertise
findable, accessible,
visible & available
when you need it

pre-registering studies

using immersive VR to
enable widespread
diverse collaboration

curating and sharing
funding opportunities

crowdfunding (parts)
of your research

funding review,
revision and
improvement, not just
novelty

openly publishing
proposals

extensively searching
for existing data
before generating
your own

improving findability
by curating/tagging
research objects

having open discovery
of open access
materials

offering your service
to Q&A platforms

managing references
collaboratively

sharing your discovery
process

sharing
bookmarks/favourites

sharing your expert
reading
recommendations

tracking associations
between 'annotations'
and subsequent text
changes/versions

sharing your
collection of
references

annotating papers,
web pages

share reading
activities in order to
make them usable as
information filter

engaging in citizen
science

making data &
software immediately
FAIR with PIDs as it is
collected/generated

working with citizen
science in academia

real time sharing of
experiments through
video

sharing workflows
openly, online

sharing notebooks
openly, online

clarifying and
specifically
communicating
materials and
methods

sharing protocols
openly, online

discussing
methodology/results
early (e.g. on blogs)

sharing scripts of your
analysis, openly online

documenting your
analysis to allow full
reproducibility

getting help to check
the reporting of your
statistical analysis

writing collaboratively

having open lab tests
and so avoid being
influenced by external
parties

drafting openly, online

using easily attainable
(open source)
software to allow
anyone to reproduce
your results

publishing actionable
papers including
executable code and
configurable
visualizations

using a collaborative
authoring
environment

coding collaboratively

making sure that all
available info is also
available to machines

making citing 2-way:
link back/track back

having executable,
forkable publications,
including text, code
and data

enabling “deep citing”
at sentence/word
level

sharing research
relationships as
research objects

spending money on
translations

citing OA versions of
literature

translating research
objects in world
languages

provide data/code
citations

archiving & sharing
data

archiving & sharing
code

storing data in the
most open format
possible

sharing executable
scripts people can
inject their own data
in

sharing all data when
we can, explaining
limitations when not
possible

archiving & sharing
video

sharing steps,
packaging bits for
reproduction

archiving & sharing
sound recordings

depositing papers in
an institutional
repository

sharing all papers as
preprints and calling
these publications

depositing papers in a
preprint archive

depositing papers in a
subject repository

archiving & sharing
PhD theses

archiving & sharing
publications

archiving & sharing
book manuscripts

archiving & sharing
master/bachelor
theses

sharing posters online
at same time as
physical presentation

publish pre-
publication history
(versions + peer
reviews)

archiving & sharing
presentations

publishing pre-prints
to encourage
feedback / informal
open peer review

openly sharing your
presentation slides
etc. on day of
presentation

live blogging /
tweeting from
conferences etc.

refusing to be part of
all male or all white
panels

doing live demo's at
conferences

testing reproducibility
with peers as part of
publishing process

selecting journal to
submit to based on
openness
characteristics

sharing peer review
reports openly

non-anonymous peer
reviewing (names
published)

encouraging
transparent peer
review (& responses)

using non-journal
organized peer review

declaring conflicts of
interest in
publications

claiming credit for
peer review

using systematic
versioning for
publications

making conflicts of
interest transparent

publishing
Open Access

specifying
contributorship roles

publishing papers in
journals that judge
only for rigour, not
novelty

using open licenses
such as CC-BY
or GNU-PL

publishing
Open Access
in hybrid journals

flipping journals to
become fully Open
Access

writing lay summaries

presenting and giving
demo's for children
(e.g. in
primary/secondary
education)

having clear
communication of
current research

involving students,
the lay public
and communicators
in science
communication

making sure that
research objects are
understandable by all
who need to
understand them

incorporating
practices of service
into workflow
(e.g.: teaching,
inclusivity)

writing plain language
abstracts

having extra material
(videos, slide ready
figures, lay public
figures, using
Wikimedia)

presenting for the
general public

writing for general
magazines/newspapers

appearing on radio or
television

creating dedicated
outreach video

using altmetrics for
monitoring outreach

writing about (your)
research in social
media

blogging and tweeting
about every stage of
the process

reacting to messages
in social media on
your topic

creating/maintaining
an online researcher
profile

communicating
analyzed data with
experts, non-expert
scientists and the lay-
public

using academic social
networks to showcase
your research output

learning from /
engaging with
communities

having a living
knowledge network

using academic social
networks to find and
communicate with
other researchers

making re-use and
licensing/citation
guidelines explicit

using author IDs

writnig/sharing
post-pub peer review

commenting openly,
online

visualizing how, why,
what for, by whom
research results
were used

having an open,
interoperable,
transferable
annotation layer over
all scholarly objects

using book level data
to assess research

using narrative
approaches to assess
research

using usage /
readership data to
assess research

using openness data
to assess research

broadly considering all
science when using
parameters for
calculating science

using metrics of
commercial/social
application to assess
research

having all types of
review openly
available

using altmetrics to
assess research